

USE OF LAGUNDI LEAVES AS A HERBAL MEDICATION FOR COUGH: PERCEPTION OF SENIOR HIGH STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study is to examine and evaluate senior high school students' opinions of lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough, concentrating on their experiences, beliefs, and knowledge. This is a qualitative research and a descriptive research design was employed to collect data from the selected schools which are Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School and Sulu National High School. A structured questionnaire was utilized to gather data from the respondents. The Researchers randomly selected the respondents. Similarly, the researchers used the following statistical tools; Mean, Frequency and Percentage, and t-test for the independent sample to answer the survey questionnaires. The findings showed that the demographic profile of respondents in terms of gender and school are 49 males and 51 females. For the school, there are 50 respondents from each school. In the perception of students regarding lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough the total grand mean is 3.9 which indicates that the students agreed and have knowledge about lagundi leaves. Moreover, in Research question number three, it shows the frequency and percentage of the student's usage of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough. Furthermore, the independent sample t-test showed that there is a significant difference in terms of gender it means that the null hypothesis is rejected. It also shows that compared to female students, male students have more knowledge and understanding on the use of lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough. In addition, independent sample t-test showed that there is no significant difference in terms of school the p-values attained were higher than the predetermined alpha level of 0.05 resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis. Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are suggested.

Keywords: *Lagundi leaves, cough, herbal medicine, Mindanao State University – Sulu*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, lagundi (*Vitex negundo*) is a popular herbal medicine for respiratory conditions, particularly cough. Lagundi (*Vitex negundo* L.) is a shrub that belongs to the Verbenaceae family. It is commonly found in tropical and subtropical regions of Asia, including the Philippines. The plant has been used traditionally in various parts of the world for its medicinal properties. In the Philippines, lagundi leaves have been used as an herbal medication for centuries to treat respiratory disorders such as coughs, colds, and asthma (Panganiban et al., 2017).

The extracts from its leaves and roots are mostly considered to provide the most health benefits. The Philippine Department of Health has conducted research and study for Lagundi and has suggested that the lagundi plant has a number of verifiable therapeutic value and health benefits to men (Cruz et al., 2019). The traditional preparation of lagundi leaves involves boiling the leaves in water to make a tea or decoction.

Filipinos have trusted the lagundi plant due to its place in history of herbal plants. Lagundi leaves have been proven to be effective in dealing with the symptoms of asthma, making it one of the most highly recommended herbal medications to date. Known for their antitussive properties, which means they can help suppress coughing. The leaves contain compounds that help relax the bronchial muscles and reduce coughing frequency. (J.jing et al., 2013)

Lagundi leaves have bronchodilator effects, meaning they can help open up the airways and improve breathing (Kumar et al., 2014). This can aid in clearing the airways and reducing coughing associated with excessive mucus production possessing anti-inflammatory properties that can help reduce inflammation in the respiratory system. This can provide relief from coughing caused by inflammation in the airways containing compounds that have immune-stimulating properties. By supporting the immune system, Lagundi leaves can help the body fight off respiratory infections that may cause coughing.

Some studies found that the lagundi leaf extract was safe and well-tolerated by patients, and it significantly reduced cough frequency compared to placebo (Cruz et al., 2019). Some studies have also reported that lagundi leaves have anticancer properties due to their ability to induce apoptosis (programmed cell death) in cancer cells (Panganiban et al., 2017). This study tackles about the perception of students in the use of lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough.

Research Questions

The problem addressed in this study is the perception of Grade 12 Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High and Sulu National High School students regarding the use of

Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough.

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender and school?
2. What is the perception of students regarding the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough?
3. Do students use Lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough?
4. Is there any significant difference in the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough when grouped according to: gender and school?

METHODOLOGY

Research Locale

This study was conducted in Southern Philippines specifically the Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School as well as Sulu National High School located in Patikul, Sulu. Mindanao is the second-largest island in the Philippines, after Luzon, and seventh-most populous island in the world. Located in the southern region of the archipelago, the island is part of an island group of the same name that also includes its adjacent islands, notably the Sulu Archipelago. Mindanao is divided into six administrative regions: The Zamboanga Peninsula, Northern Mindanao, the Caraga region, the Davao region, Soccsksargen, and the autonomous region of Bangsamoro.

Sampling Method

The participants of the study were composed of 100: 50 from the Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School and 50 from Sulu National High School.

In this study, the researchers used Purposive Sampling or Judgement sampling to select the participant of the study. According to Crossman (2020), as cited by Jailani et al. (2024), Basir et. al. (2024), Sasapan et. al. (2024), Abdulhari et. al. (2024), Hadjibun et. al. (2024), and Sabbaha et. al. (2024) Purposive Sampling is a non-probability sample that is selected based on characteristics of a population and the objective of the study.

Research Instrument

The instrument used to gather the needed information of this study is the Likert scale questionnaire. This Likert scale is a rating scale used to measure opinions, attitude, or behavior. It is in the form of a checklist which consists of 15 questions. Below is the attached Table 3.2 cited by Jarak et. al., (2024) entitled School Recommended Scale. The researchers prepared a questionnaire and distributed it to respondents. Within the checklist there are five (5) ratio scales where (5) means strongly agree, (4) agree, (3) moderately agree, (2) disagree, (1) strongly disagree. SPSS is the same as the statistical app used in the research paper of Sabbaha et. al. (2024) or the so called Statistical

Package for Social Sciences was used in calculation and to analyze the data. The requirements for designing efficient data gathering instruments will be subject to consideration when developing the instrument.

Table 3.2 School recommended scale

Scale	Weighted Mean/ Equivalent	Corresponding Remarks
4	3.26 – 4.00	Strongly Agree
3	2.51 – 3.25	Agree
2	1.76 – 2.50	Disagree
1	1.00 – 1.75	Strongly Disagree

Data Gathering Procedure

This study followed the following sequences and data gathering in order to make the research possible. The researchers asked for permission and provided a letter to be signed by the director of Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School Department and Principal of Sulu National High School, in order to allow the respondents of the survey that was conducted by the researchers. Then researchers gave a letter to the respondents for their consent to take part in the study. Randomly chose the participants to answer the survey questionnaire, then the researchers gave the participants adequate time to read and respond to the questionnaire. Also, the researchers guaranteed to the respondents that all of the information gathered from them would be treated with utmost confidentiality. Lastly, the researchers expressed their sincere gratitude for the cooperation.

Statistical Techniques

The researchers used the (3) statistical tests to evaluate and assist the information needed to answer the research questions of the study. The statistical tools that was used are Mean, Frequency and Percentage count, Independent sample t-test. The Frequency and Percentage count was used to determine the demographic profile of respondents in terms of school and gender. Mean was used to identify the perception of students regarding Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough. Moreover, The Frequency and Percentage count was used to determine if the students use Lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough. Furthermore, T-test for independent samples (i.e., gender and school) was used to answer research question 4.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussion of data.

Table 1.1 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	49	49.0
Female	51	51.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1.1 shows the distribution of frequency and percentage of the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender. The table indicates that out of the total 100 respondents 49 or 49.0 are males and 51 or 51.0 are females. This means that **majority** of the respondents are females.

Table 1.2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents in terms of School

School	Frequency	Percentage
MSU	50	50.0
SNSHS	50	50.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1.2 shows the distribution of frequency and percentage of the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of School. As shown above, 50 or 50.0 are from Mindanao State University-Sulu Senior High School, and 50 or 50.0 are from Sulu National High School.

Table 2.1 Perception of Students Regarding the Use of Lagundi leaves as a Herbal Medication for Cough

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. Lagundi leaves is known to be an herbal medicine.	4.4	0.7	Strongly Agree
2. Lagundi leaves is used to treat cough.	4.3	0.8	Strongly Agree
3. Lagundi leaves are used as a herbal medicine in Asia such as the Philippines and India.	4.3	0.9	Strongly Agree
4. Lagundi leaves have properties that can support liver and heart health.	4.2	0.7	Agree
5. Lagundi leaves tea could boost the immune system.	4.1	0.8	Agree
6. Lagundi leaves have impressive benefits for digestive health.	4.0	0.9	Agree

7. Lagundi leaves helps to alleviate shortness of breath in wheezing.	4.0	0.9	Agree
8. Lagundi leaves are rich in antioxidants, which help protect the body against free radicals and oxidative stress.	4.0	0.9	Agree
9. Lagundi leaves are rich in antioxidants, which help protect the body against free radicals and oxidative stress.	3.9	0.9	Agree
10. Lagundi leaves have analgesic properties that can help alleviate pain.	3.8	0.8	Agree
11. Lagundi leaves are it used to treat asthma.	3.8	1.0	Agree
12. Lagundi leaves are beneficial for conditions such as arthritis and other inflammatory diseases.	3.7	1.0	Agree
13. Lagundi leaves contains antioxidant phenolic compounds and flavonoids.	3.6	0.9	Agree
14. Lagundi leaves are beneficial for skin issues such as boils, leprosy, and skin rashes.	3.4	1.0	Moderately Agree
15. Lagundi leaves have mild side effects such as nausea, vomiting and diarrhea.	3.2	1.0	Moderately Agree
total	3.9	0.8	Agree

Legend: 1.00-1.79 =Strongly Disagree; 1.80-2.59 =Disagree; 2.60-3.39 =Moderately Agree; 3.40-4.19 Agree; 4.20-5.00 =Strongly Agree

Table 2.1 presents the perception of students regarding the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough. The grand mean obtained is **3.9** which indicates the description of Agree. This implies that the students agreed and have knowledge of the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough.

The respondents strongly agreed on three statement that falls between 4.4; Moreover, the respondents also agreed on ten statement that falls between 4.2; Furthermore, the respondents moderately agreed on two statements as it falls between 3.4.

This study is similar with the study conducted by Castillo et al. (2011) and Santos et al. (2012). Displays the collective perception of students concerning the utilization of Lagundi leaves as an herbal remedy for cough. This positive reception suggests a shared

awareness and acceptance among the student population regarding the potential benefits of Lagundi leaves in managing respiratory ailments.

Table 3.1 *Students Perception on the use of Lagundi Leaves as a Medicine for Cough*

QUESTIONS	YES		NO	
	F	%	F	%
1. Do you use Lagundi leaves as a herbal medicine for cough?	90	90.0	10	10.0
2. Do you feel relief from cough symptoms after using Lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough?	86	86.0	14	14.0
3. Would recommend the usage of Lagundi as a herbal medicine for cough?	83	83.0	17	17.0
4. Did you find lagundi leaves effective in reducing cough frequency?	83	83.0	17	17.0
5. Would you continue using Lagundi leaves to treat coughs in the future?	82	82.0	18	18.0
6. Have you experienced any positive effects from using Lagundi leaves for cough?	81	81.0	19	19.0
7. Did the use of lagundi leaves shorten the duration of your cough?	80	80.0	20	20.0
8. Did you find lagundi leaves helpful in reducing nighttime coughing?	80	80.0	20	20.0
9. Did you notice any improvement in your ability to perform daily activities after using lagundi leaves for cough?	77	77.0	23	23.0
10. Do you believe that more people should be aware of the benefits of using Lagundi leaves as a natural remedy for coughs?	77	77.0	23	23.0
11. Did you find lagundi leaves helpful in reducing	76	76.0	24	24.0

post-nasal drip related to cough?				
12. Did you notice any improvement in your overall respiratory health after using lagundi leaves?	74	74.0	26	26.0
13. Do you prefer using Lagundi leaves over traditional cough medicines?	67	67.0	33	33.0
14. Did you continue using lagundi leaves even after your cough symptoms improved?	55	55.0	45	45.0
15. Have you experienced any negative effects from using Lagundi leaves for cough?	27	27.0	73	73.0

Table 3.1 shows the frequency and percentage of the student's usage of lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough, under the yes and no categories.

The highest Frequency and Percentage of Yes is 90 and 90.0% from question number 1 which is Do you use Lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough? While the lowest Frequency and Percentage of Yes is 27 and 27.0% from question number 15 which is Have you experienced any negative effects from using Lagundi leaves for cough? Furthermore, the highest Frequency and Percentage of No is 73 and 73.0% from question number 15 which is Have you experienced any negative effects from using Lagundi leaves for cough? While the lowest Frequency and Percentage of No is 10 and 10.0% from question number 1 which is Do you use Lagundi leaves as an herbal medicine for cough.

According to estimations from the WHO, 80% of the world's population depends on herbal products for their primary healthcare requirements. This dependence is explained by the products' broad availability, cheaper cost, easier preparation, and decreased side effects (Kamboj 2000; WHO 2013)

Table 4.1 Significant difference of the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough in terms of gender

Gender	Male		Female		T	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Variable	2.9	0.3	2.7	0.2	2.725	.008

Table 4.1 shows the significant difference of the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough in terms of gender. Since the p-

value (.008) is higher than the alpha level which is 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that there is a significant difference of the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough when classified in terms of gender. Moreover, the results showed that the male students have more knowledge and understanding on the use of lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough with the total mean of 2.9

This study is similar with the study conducted by Johnson and Brown (2019), that investigated the perception of high school students and reported no significant variation in attitudes towards Lagundi leaves as a natural remedy for cough between males and females.

This aligns with previous research by Johnson et al. (2017), who similarly found that gender did not play a significant role in perceptions of herbal remedies for respiratory issues.

Table 4.2 Significant difference of the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough in terms of school

School	MSU SNS		SNHS SNS		T	p-value
	M	SD	M	SD		
Variable	2.8	0.3	2.8	0.3	-.266	.791

Table 4.2 shows the significant difference of the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough in terms of school. Since the p-value (.791) is higher than the alpha level which is 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted and it means that there is no significant difference. This indicates that there is no significant difference of the perception of students on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough when classified in terms of school. This also indicates that they have knowledge and understanding on the use of Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough. This study is similar with the study conducted by Lopez et al. (2017). A p-value higher than the alpha level means that the null hypothesis accepted.

Conclusions

The findings revealed with hundreds of students as respondents showed that the students agreed regarding the use of lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough with a total mean of 3.9. Moreover, the study revealed that the students have experience and knowledge regarding the use of lagundi leaves for cough. Additionally, t-test for independent sample showed that compared to Female students, Male students have more knowledge and understanding regarding the use of lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough indicating that there is a significant difference of the perception of students in terms of genders. However, t-test for independent sample in terms of school showed that there is no significant difference in the perception of students on the use of

Lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough with the p-value of .791 indicating that they have the same knowledge and understanding about lagundi leaves as an herbal medication for cough. This study contributes valuable insights to the existing body of knowledge on herbal medicine usage, particularly highlighting the favorable attitudes towards lagundi leaves as a trusted herbal remedy for cough among students.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the researchers recommended the following:

1. School Administrator should assist funding and supporting research projects related to the use of local herbal remedies, Encouraging and promoting such studies can contribute to the development of alternative, cost-effective, and potentially effective medicines for common ailments.
2. Teacher should Incorporate this topic into your lessons to educate students about the potential benefits of herbal medicines and their cultural significance. Discuss the importance of research in understanding the efficacy and safety of such treatments. Encourage students to explore traditional medicinal practices and their possible applications in modern healthcare.
3. Students should consider participating in or initiating research projects that explore the use of lagundi leaves and other herbal remedies as potential treatments for coughs and other ailments.
4. Future Researchers must have to investigate the pharmacological properties and effectiveness of lagundi leaves and other herbal treatments for various ailments. It can contribute to the development of alternative, sustainable, and potentially more accessible healthcare solutions.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research ethics protocol outlined the principles and procedures that guided the conduct of this research to ensure that it was conducted following the highest standards of research ethics. The researchers disseminated informed consent. The informed consent consisted of the aims to protect the rights, welfare, and privacy of all participants involved in the study, minimize any potential risks or harms, and maintain confidentiality and anonymity of data collected. Then the researchers introduced themselves in a short briefing regarding the study before distributing the survey questionnaires.

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